

PROVINGS OF *CARCINOSIN*

By DR. W. LEES TEMPLETON

It is generally admitted that provings are the basis of the Homœopathic Materia Medicas and there is nothing which has a greater propaganda effect than the information that provings are still being made, and especially when the drug is one which one's hearers know something about. Those, e.g., of *Strophanthus* were of especial value in arousing interest, and in suggesting to sceptics that there is something in Homœopathy. One must speak to them in their own language and the experimental method, as exemplified in provings, using controls which they all understand, does register especially with students fresh from the physiological laboratories upon whom the impact of clinical successes has no effect at all.

Nosodes have rarely been fully proved, or as fully as other substances, and the paucity of information about the source of the symptomatology of almost all of our nosodes is amazing, even in books devoted to them. It would be useful if someone with the time and opportunity could trace the source of these if only to answer the inevitable enquiry. Even with our present substance *Carcinosin* its source is unknown to Nelson, who have supplied our material. All they can say is that it comes from U.S.A., but we ought to know the sources of our remedies.

The following remarks are culled from the complete symptomatology which will be printed in full, but will give those who only know the clinical picture, such as it is, the opportunity of comparing what they have found useful with those obtained by provings. I have not acquainted myself with any published records of *Carcinosin*, as I believe it is essential for the Director of provings to be like Cæsar's wife, above suspicion, when taking the records of such provings.

Mental symptoms

They all complained of a feeling of remoteness, if spoken to, could not reply. They were forgetful, which, in the particular individuals, was uncommon. They felt dull, disinterested. There was an aversion to conversation—having to make oneself think was an effort. They were irritable because they were forgetful and found concentration difficult.

Head symptoms

There was a sensation of thumping, mostly on the right side. The brain felt tight, again leading to a condition of aversion to conversation. This tight feeling seems to be rather general. There was tightness and constriction. It is interesting that, as a director of provings, one thinks there is nothing in this and, yet, when you read through the descriptions, one began to see a little thread of similarity running through a number of provers. It is not all wishful thinking because it seems to come as a surprise. This feeling of constriction shows itself running through various regions of the body. Other symptoms are throbbing pain deep inside the head, the depth was very marked. There was twitching of the eyelids and a twitching of various muscle groups seems to be a marked feature and can be taken as a general.

Ear, Nose and Throat

Sore throat, very much like *Lachesis*, worse for warmth and better for cold; that goes through quite a number. Localization was to the palate "as if there was a lump", a soreness of the palate, which is rather unusual with most sore throats. Sore throat on swallowing saliva, worse in the morning, better as the day goes on, comes on again at night, is again very like *Lachesis*.

Respiratory

A cough (which hurt the stomach) from a tickling in the throat, a tickling cough at night, keeps on clearing the throat, worse for talking, worse for singing, worse

for being in a warm room, and worse in the morning when dressing or washing or shaving—I could not follow whether that would come under “from exposure of the body”. The cough was worse for stretching the throat, as in yawning. That is trivial but it is often the trivial signs which matter. I had a case the other day of a patient with a very severe torticollis and the aggravation was on yawning. An anatomist might be able to explain it, but there is only one drug which had it, *Nat. sulph.* I gave *Nat. sulph.* which cured the torticollis. Cough and soreness in the throat, worse undressing, a stomach cough, worse in a stuffy room, irritation in the pharynx, larynx and in the thyroid, aggravated on leaving the cold air, from dressing in the morning, and another trivial symptom, soreness in the palate, was again prominent.

Heart

There were very few symptoms. Throbbing again was general; “can feel the heart and hear it lying down”; again as if the heart were constricted. A tightness as if one wants to sigh, like *Ignatia*.

Stomach and Rectum

Constipation marked, “much more constipated than usual”, “never been so constipated”, very little desire for stool, stool very dry, difficult to expel, like *Opium*. This seemed to be a general finding. There were pains in the back and pains in the extremities, twitching of the muscles of the arm, the eyebrows and eyelids, a jerking and jumping and a sensation of tingling. A weak, tired feeling in the legs especially in the late evening, which was particularly marked. One said, “If I have a short sleep I wake up absolutely on top of the world and I can stay up to 2 or 3 in the morning”; also “if I fight that tiredness and so not have a short sleep I can after a short period settle down at my books with the same degree of energy”. If he kept occupied he *could* work it off, but if he had a short sleep he awoke feeling well. Aching, like toothache, in the shoulder muscles, better for warmth and movement, pain in the legs, better for *gentle* movement, worse for *quick* movement, aching back of the thighs with tingling and twitching on the back, worse if wet, aching arms and legs, aching back, arms and legs, worse for sitting still, all very like *Rhus tox.*

Skin

Return of old eczema, apparently a seborrheal irritation in the sternum and between the shoulders, had never been so bad, much worse on undressing. Again we get that story of undressing.

Sleep

Restless, difficulty in getting off to sleep, dreams of drifting, dreams of looking for someone and failing to find them, a long time getting off, wakes up tired, restless, disturbed, *twitching* of muscles, light sleep, mind much too active, wakes up after exhausting dreams.

Trying to analyse these and give you a picture of the drug, in the mental symptoms we get forgetfulness, aversion to conversation, black-outs. Among the physical symptoms are headaches, jumping throbbing muscles, mostly right side, pain deep inside the head, a feeling of tightness and constriction, twitching of the eyes, sore throat, a lump sensation with soreness of the palate. There was tenderness in the gums and aching on the teeth. There was a respiratory cough and a stomach cough, dry tickling in the throat, worse in the cold or on the change from warm to cold or cold to warm, worse for talking, worse when dressing, worse when undressing, that is *Rumex*, worse for stretching of the throat. Heart throbbing, a feeling all the time as if one were constricted, this is in the stomach, abdomen and rectum. Pain better for pressure and for hot drinks like *Phos*. Constipation with lack of desire, which is *Opium*.

One of the marked features of the mental symptoms was the weak, tired

feeling which was better for a short sleep but which could be overcome by a strong mental effort. Pains in the legs, better for warmth and gentle movement reminds one of *Pulsatilla* and *Rhus alb.* The symptom of the skin worse for undressing reminds one of *Rumex*. The sleep difficulty, disturbed sleep, waking up twitching, awake most of the night, reminds one again of *Pulsatilla*.

PROVINGS OF *CARCINOSIN*, 1952/53

1st Group : 4 provers, 4 controls. Preparations used were *Carcinosin* 30 and 200.

MENTALS

Fogged, absent-minded. Does not respond to talking though aware of hearing it. Effort to think clearly. Slow, dull.

HEAD

Dull, heavy, frontal ache worse 7 p.m., right side temple, as if someone pressing there. Thumping headache behind eyebrows 1 to 6 p.m., heavy between temples all day. Confused feeling right frontal regions and vertex to occiput.

EYES

Strained. Stye which discharged.

EAR, NOSE AND THROAT

Excoriating nasal discharge. Stuffy nose with thick discharge like lump in larynx. Sore throat when not swallowing (L).

MOUTH

Aching at roots of teeth. Mouth ulcer with foul taste. Tender gums with stiff jaw.

RESPIRATORY

Cough which hurts stomach from tickling throat pit, with soreness trachea and sternum worse 8 to 11 p.m. Tickling cough worse at night. Keeps on clearing throat before being able to speak. No expectoration. Tickling in throat pit worse talking, singing, indoors or warm room, stabbing pain behind sternum worse rising a.m., worse when washing a.m., worse stretching throat as, e.g., yawning. Cough from tickling in throat pit worse laughing, worse warm room, better cool air.

STOMACH, ABDOMEN AND RECTUM

Constipation with heavy pain above umbilicus, comes slowly, goes slowly, worse 4 to 6 p.m. Irregular motions. More constipated than usual. Pain low down abdomen with flatus per rectum; upward eructations tasting of vomit. Much flatus and much less desire for stool.

BACK

Pains left angle of shoulder blade. Pain right side of neck worse turning to right.

EXTREMITIES

Twitching muscles of thigh, arms, brow, eyelids; actually move and jump, with sensation of tingling. Weak tired feeling, especially in legs (though tired mind and body) in late evening, better if kept active, could be worked off; also better after short sleep, woke completely refreshed and able to work for hours. Similarly, if kept active and did not rest. Aching like toothache shoulder muscles, amel. warmth and movement. Rheumatic pains legs amel. warmth and gentle movement, agg. quick movement.

SKIN

Return of old eczematous signs (not since childhood). Seborrhœic eruption sternum and between shoulders, irritable, agg. while undressing, amel. scratching.

SLEEP

Restless. Difficulty in getting off to sleep. Dreams of working, travelling, looking for someone.

GENERALS

Aggravation generally 6 to 7 p.m.
As if cold coming on, which it didn't.
Amel. cool air, agg. warm room.

SYMPTOMS WHICH PROVINGERS THOUGHT WERE QUITE NEW

Stomach pains. Constipation. Rash chest and back. Cough. Muscle twitching. Evening tiredness. Poorness of memory. Tiredness, mental and physical.

2nd Group : 5 provers, 4 controls.

MENTALS

Tired physically, irritable, depressed. Dull, disinterested, averse to conversation, forgetfulness (returned thrice for spectacles), difficulty in concentrating, forgetful of normal things, must think deliberately; irritable because he is forgetful. Forgetful too easily.

HEAD

Dazed, dizzy, heavy, frontal region (could not take anything in). Brain felt tight, heavy over eyes, better open air; heavy behind right eye, averse conversation. Occiput affected left to right; eye better closing eyes, better pressure. Heavy full head, drowsy, sleepy, difficult concentration. Frontal headache. Throbbing occiput deep inside head worse motion, left side from vertex.

- EYES**
Sore lid margins, *twitching* left lower lid, ache behind right eye, tender to pressure, edges of lids sore and dry. Stinging upper lids.
- EAR, NOSE AND THROAT**
Inflamed lobe right ear. Sensation as if ear blocked, inflamed meatal wall. Sore throat, worse empty swallowing and warm drinks. Sore throat on waking, worse salivation, better cold. Throat *as if lump* in soft *palate*, sore, worse salivation a.m. and p.m., better daytime. Sore *palate*, worse a.m.
- RESPIRATORY**
Cough from dryness in throat; *throat pit* worse cold; stomach cough whilst talking, clogs up then clears with cough, dryness better coughing, worse undressing; stomach cough. Cough worse *indoors*. Cough worse talking, *stuffy room, cold air*, whilst eating. Cough from irritation, *larynx, pharynx and palate*, from laughing, *cold air*, inspiration while dressing a.m. Sore *palate* a.m. Shortness of breath on running.
- HEART**
Throbbing 2 to 6 p.m., can hear and feel heart beat, worse lying down. Stitching pain on standing. Sensation as if heart constricted, *tightness as if wants to sigh*; palpitation on running.
- STOMACH, ABDOMEN AND RECTUM**
Mouth ulcer upper gum and side of tongue. Nausea travelling by bus, tight constricting pain, better pressure and bending and hot drinks. *Dry hard* stools, painful to pass. *Constipation* with flatus. *Very constipated*, painful to pass; bleeding increased piles. Diarrhoea for two days only.
- BACK AND EXTREMITIES**
Aching back of thighs, with numbness and tingling of arms and legs if crosses arms or bends arms. Hands go white and blue. Twitches in the back; pain right and left hips worse for motion and worse if weight off the legs. Aching arms and legs, acute coldness hands and feet, aching back; arms and legs *worse for cold and sitting still*.
- SLEEP**
Long in getting off; wakes up frequently; *restless*; *tired*, in spite of good sleep. *Restless, disturbed sleep*. Twitching wakes him (general twitching). Light sleep, keeps on waking up. Tired, but mind too active to sleep quickly, takes an hour and three-quarters to get off. Waking 4 a.m. *Awake most of the night with exciting dreams*.
- GENERALS**
Tiredness in spite of adequate sleep. Less talkative, worse stuffy room, better open air. Forgetfulness. Tiredness. Coldness extremities, worse draught.
- MARKED SYMPTOMS NOTED BY PROVERS**
Boils. Mouth ulcers. Pins and needles extremities. Frontal headaches. Cough, worse in the morning. Sore throat, worse empty swallowing. Acne of face. Hip pains. Sleeplessness.

Group 1

Group 2

- | | |
|--|---|
| MENTALS | |
| Dull. Fogged. | Dull. Averse to conversation. |
| Effort to think. Doesn't respond to conversation, but aware of it. | Can't take anything in. |
| | Must think deliberately. |
| | Difficult concentration. |
| | Irritable. Forgetful. |
| HEAD | |
| Frontal. Heavy. Dull. Right. | Frontal. Heavy. Right. |
| | Occiput to deep inside eyes. |
| | Behind eyes. |
| EYES | |
| Strained. <i>Stye</i> . | Sore lid margins. Dry. |
| Twitching of eyebrow and lids. | Stinging. Twitching lid. |
| MOUTH | |
| Ulcer and foul taste. | Ulcer upper lip and side of tongue. |
| EAR | |
| | Inflammation right lobe. |
| | Inflammation meatal wall. |
| NOSE | |
| Discharge—acid—thick. | |
| THROAT | |
| Pain. <i>Lump</i> worse NOT swallowing. | Pain, worse empty swallowing. |
| Tender gums. | Pain palate " <i>as if lump</i> ". Sore. Throat-pit and larynx. |
| RESPIRATORY | |
| Tickling cough. <i>Throat pit</i> . | <i>Throat pit and larynx</i> . |
| Pain retrosternal. | Cough with dryness. |
| Agg. nights 8-11 p.m. and "Nights". | Agg. warm room, cold air, talking and laughing. |
| Agg. warm room. | |

RESPIRATORY (*continued*)

Stomach cough, *agg. talking and laughing*.
Keeps on clearing throat before being able to speak.

Clogs while talking, ameliorated by coughing.

RECTUM

Constipation ; *lack of desire*.
Flatus.

Constipation. Flatus.
Diarrhoea (2 days).

EXTREMITIES

Twitching muscles—thighs, arms, brow, eyelids.

Twitching back.
Tingling. Cold extremities.

Tingling.

Aching pain. *agg. movement and warmth*, in legs, thighs and shoulder.

Aching pain, agg. cold, rest, and movement, in arms, legs, hips and thighs.

SLEEP

Restless. Difficulty in getting off.
Dreams of travelling, looking for someone.
Active mind.
Amel. short sleep.

Difficulty in getting off.
Exciting dreams.
Active mind.
Tired in spite of good sleep.

GENERAL

Thumping (headache).
Time *agg.* 1-6 p.m. headache.
4-6 p.m. abdominal pain.
Skin irritable, *agg. undressing*.

Throbbing (heart).
Throbbing (occiput).
2-6 p.m. throbbing heart.
Cough, *agg. undressing*.

RÉSUMÉ OF CARCINOSIN SYMPTOMS

MENTALS

Fogged ; aware but does not register. Must think deliberately. Forgets normal things like spectacles (went back three times). Concentration difficult. Dull, disinterested, averse conversation.

HEAD

Thumping. Throbbing headaches, right sided, over right eye, deep inside head (cf. *Tub.*).
Brain felt tight.

EYES

Twitching lids.

EAR, NOSE AND THROAT

Sensation like a *lump* ; soreness of *palate*, *agg. empty swallow, agg. warm drinks, amel. cold* ; *agg. a.m. and p.m. (cf. Lachesis)*.

MOUTH

Tender gums, aching teeth, ulcers.

RESPIRATORY

Cough ; stomach cough (cf. *Bry.*), from tickling *respiratory pit*. *Agg. warmth, warm room, cold air (cf. Rumex)* ; *agg. laughing, talking (cf. Phos., Rumex)* ; *agg. when dressing and undressing (cf. Rumex)* ; *agg. stretching throat when yawning (cf. Nat. sulph.)*.

HEART

Violent throbbing, can hear it, can feel it. (cf. *Spigelia*).

As if heart constricted (see Head).

Tightness as if wants to sigh (*Ign.*).

STOMACH, ABDOMEN, RECTUM

Tight constricting (again), pain *amel. pressure, bending, hot drinks (cf. Mag. phos.)*.

Constipation, lacks desire (*Opium*).

Dry hard stools (*Opium*).

BACK AND EXTREMITIES

Twitching muscles in thighs, arms and in the back (see eyelids and eyebrows).

Aching, weak, tired, numb feeling in thighs, better for short sleep, awoke completely refreshed (very marked), but if did not rest but pushed himself to it could overcome it (cf. the effort to think).

Pains legs, *amel. warmth and gentle movement (cf. Puls.)* ; *agg. QUICK movement*.

SKIN

Acneiform eruptions face.

Rash between shoulders *agg. undressing* (see cough).

SLEEP

Restless. Difficulty in getting off (cf. *Puls.*).

Disturbed ; wakened by *twitching* (again) ; exciting dreams ; mind too active (cf. *Coffea*) ; awake most of the night.

REPORT ON STOOL CULTURES—PROVERS

September 1952—March 1953

Since the end of September, a total of 90 Stool Cultures have been made and typed.

A.C.T.H.	..	..	27
Controls	..	..	39
<i>Carcinosin</i>	..	..	24
			—
			90

The following table shows the distribution of the abnormalities detected:

	No Growth	1-4 Colonies	Cocci	Yeast	Proteus	Morgan	Gaertner
<i>Carcinosin</i> ..	5 ¹	2 ¹	5 ¹	2 ¹	1 (20%)	—	—
A.C.T.H. ..	1	1	1	—	1 (1%)	(50%) (60%) (80%)	1 (3%)
Controls ..	1 ²	2 ²	3 ²	1 ²	—	—	—
Total ³ ..	6	4	8	1	1	3	1

¹—Includes one each isolated in the Control Period.

²—Includes one each isolated following administration of *Carcinosin*.

³—Allowances being made for the duplication—see ¹ and ².

Conclusion

- (1) *Carcinosin* and A.C.T.H. do appear to alter the bowel flora.
- (2) A high proportion of "no growth" cocci and "Yeast" are associated with *Carcinosin* and may be of long duration.
- (3) B. Morgan is associated in high proportion with A.C.T.H.

COPY OF THE LATE DR. PATERSON'S LETTER ON CONCLUSIONS OF BOWEL FLORA STUDIES IN PROVERS

20th May, 1953.

I think your conclusions are quite in order, but I would suggest that a further observation be made in this series as in others there is:

(a) Evidence of change of bowel flora to non-lactose type.

(b) This change to N.L.F. does *not* bear specific relationship to the drug given, when 'proving' on a healthy individual (*cf.* Drug relationship with N.L.F. in the sick person).

In the 'proving' it is a struggle between the drug energy and that of the 'healthy' patient—hence the variation in type. This has been evident in all the 'provings' so far carried out.

(c) In controls there were *no N.L.F. found*.

(d) In 'provings' there were 5 changes to N.L.F. (A big percentage of the total cases.)

I agree that the 'no growth' and the 'cocci' are also worth noting and the *persistence* of the change also.

Wishing you all success in this work,

Yours sincerely,
(Signed) JOHN PATERSON.

Explanatory note: N.L.F. is the contraction for 'Non-Lactose Fermenting Organisms.'

Dr. FOUBISTER thanked Dr. Templeton for his account of the proving which had been presented in such an interesting manner. Dr. Templeton had

the rare gift of making provings really interesting. Dr. Foubister said he had proved *Carcinosin* on himself, taking the 200th potency of the same preparation obtained at Nelsons which had been used in the official proving. The symptoms were frontal headache extending into the eyes, and insomnia, late in falling asleep, frequent wakings, and finally waking about 4 a.m. after which no further sleep could be obtained. *Carcinosin* was a very useful remedy when indicated in insomnia. An infant of six months had suffered from insomnia for three months and the parents were worn out. After a month of careful but ineffective prescribing, *Carcinosin* 200 night and morning for five nights, then night only for five nights, cured the insomnia. It had to be repeated once about six months later, when a single dose was effective. Dr. Foubister said he was at present making a clinical study of *Carcinosin* and found that insomnia was present in a high percentage of histories, even in children, when *Carcinosin* was otherwise indicated. He had become interested in *Carcinosin* about two years ago, because two children were attending out-patients whose mothers had suffered from carcinoma of breast during the period of gestation. The mothers subsequently died. These two children, though apparently quite unrelated, presented a striking similarity in appearance. Both children had blue sclerotics, a café-au-lait complexion and numerous moles. Could this be regarded as a proving of a nature which could not be reproduced experimentally? He would greatly appreciate hearing from members present or anyone reading the discussion who had any similar evidence. Both these children suffered from insomnia which was relieved by *Carcinosin*.

The next step was to pick out any children of the "*Carcinosin*" appearance and go carefully into their family history. The impression was that cancer or leukæmia, tuberculosis, pernicious anæmia and diabetes were more common in such families, and a strong family history of one or more of these could be taken equally as a *Carcinosin* indication. The related remedies were *Tuberculinum* (or one of the *Tuberculins*), *Medorrhinum*, *Syphilinum* as might be expected for inherited tendencies, *Nat. mur.*, *Sepia*, *Calc. phos.*, *Phos.*, *Pulsatilla*, *Sulphur*, *Psorinum*, *Ars. alb.*, *Ars. iod.*, *Nat. sul.* and *Opium*. *Carcinosin* seemed like the bowel nosodes to cover a very wide range of the symptoms of the related remedies and when one or more of these had helped partially *Carcinosin* was likely to help further. He had, however, prescribed it as a single remedy. About half the children for whom *Carcinosin* was otherwise indicated slept in the knee-elbow position. (This position is often only present during the first year.) The majority of patients were influenced by sea air in some way. Many were improved in one place and aggravated in another; for instance, on the East and South Coast, or in a relaxing and bracing place.

There were some very characteristic cravings or aversions to food, which again showed the resemblance to the combined related remedies. There was a craving or aversion to salt, fruit, eggs, milk and fat. It was interesting, in the light of the provings, that not only was the family history a guide, but the personal history very often followed a distinct pattern in childhood. There was a tendency to have whooping-cough badly early in life, or pneumonia. Some alimentary disturbance, either gastro-enteritis, indigestion or constipation were very often present in childhood. The characteristic triad of symptoms in the early history were chest symptoms, whooping-cough severely and usually at an early age, or pneumonia, alimentary symptoms, and insomnia.

The predominance of frontal headaches in the provers, especially the tendency to be one-sided, suggested *Carcinosin* might be a remedy useful in the treatment of migraine. He had not used it in an attack, but could recall six cases in which it seemed to help greatly as a constitutional remedy. Two had been previously helped by *Tuberculinum*, three by *Sepia*, and one by *Arsenicum alb.* The *Tuberculinum* cases were sisters; one had been helped by infrequent doses of *Tuberculinum Cm.* over a period of ten years. After going into the history again and taking the appearance of the patient into consideration, *Carcinosin*

was prescribed. There was a temporary aggravation followed by vastly improved general health and appearance and freedom from migraine for over a year.

The mental dullness and inability to think easily of the provers was related clinically to the use of *Carcinosin* in backward and mentally-defective children. Mongols were nearly always helped by *Medorrhinum* and *Carcinosin* should also be considered for Mongols. Some who had been previously helped by *Medorrhinum* responded well to *Carcinosin* and others had responded to *Carcinosin* from the start. In other cases of mental defect and backwardness, *Carcinosin* had been used on the indications outlined with great benefit in some instances. It was an important constitutional remedy for children in many conditions, including recurrent colds, acidosis, asthma and infantile eczema. Ulcers in the mouth had been frequently noted, sometimes before and sometimes after administration of *Carcinosin*. An inflammatory reaction was noted in nearly 50 per cent. of cases in which *Carcinosin* was given. Regarding heart and limb symptoms, *Carcinosin* seemed to be frequently indicated in cases of rheumatic fever. The 30th-200th potencies had been most commonly prescribed in the cases studied. Latterly higher potencies had been used and with enhanced effects, especially when the remedy had been repeated as with other remedies. *Carcinosin* as a constitutional remedy had probably been often overlooked.

Dr. TEMPLETON said it was interesting that Dr. Foubister should find some confirmation in the provings of his own indications. The satisfaction of all scientific experiment was to find the unexpected.

The PRESIDENT said he would express his sorrow that no-one knew the source of *Carcinosin* and if this work brought this mass of detail to fruition it would do a great deal for the scientific aspect of homœopathy. They *must* know what they were dealing with and its origin. A very interesting point came out in Dr. Foubister's contribution, namely, the wide range of the medicines that he found to be related to the *Carcinosin* which he used (and which had been recorded by him as to its origin). That should be so because cancer affected every known type of individual, and one should find that there must be a *Carcinosin* for every electro-physical group. He thought they should go out and find these things and by that means find a greater and more valuable method of employing them.

He would like to propose a special vote of thanks to Dr. Templeton because he was carrying out most important work in the conduction of such valuable provings. He was continuing investigation into cortisone and A.C.T.H. and other substances, all of which would be a great contribution to the *Materia Medica*. When these complete drug provings were examined in detail, it would be realized that there was no other authority in the world of medicine trying to exert themselves in this invaluable research, and yet, all of us knew that Homœopathy exists because of *Drug Provings*.

He wished to express that special vote of thanks to him and he knew the members would join him in doing so.